

The book and Typhoon Yagi

Nghiem P. K. Cuong

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[BOOK REVIEW]

Typhoon Yagi has, to a large extent, shown the greatly detrimental effect of the climate crisis currently facing the Earth. The death toll in Vietnam only has surpassed most people's imagination [1], let alone the devastating impacts caused by the dangerous storm on many provinces under its trajectory.

Photo: Typhoon Yagi's aftermath in Quang Ninh, Vietnam (<https://www.nytimes.com/2024/09/09/us/typhoon-yagi-vietnam-deaths.html>)

I came to know the book by Professor Vuong Quan Hoang and Dr. Nguyen Minh Hoang in mid-July 2024. However, only when seeing the grave consequences of Typhoon Yagi, could I gradually understand the interconnectedness of phenomena, concepts, and key messages delivered in the title. There are awakening facts and arguments, which await simple-minded readers to explore when witnessing the harsh realities (most of which are likely part of the predicted consequences, no matter how hard to believe).

I do not have enough words to recommend the book. But I do believe that it can restore our environmental conscience and make everybody think, perhaps deeply.

(*) *Editorial note*: The post reprints Mr. Cuong's review of the title on Goodreads, with slight reformatting (accessed on Sept 15, 2024; <https://www.goodreads.com/book/show/216375689-better-economics-for-the-earth>)

References

[1] Dinh H, Rising D. (2024). Vietnam typhoon death toll rises to 233 as more bodies found in areas hit by landslides and floods. <https://apnews.com/article/vietnam-flooding-typhoon-yagi-deaths-95c5de93c84e636c32f2a875c77db0fa>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOD98L5K44>

